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General approach

We report how we determined our sample size, all data exclusions (if any), all manipulations, and all measures in the study ("21 word solution"). We do not report conditions, variables, analyses, or participants selectively without transparently revealing the reasoning behind the selection. We avoid the use of analysis techniques with excessive and unwarranted user-degrees of freedom.

Novel or preexisting data?

The behavioral data have already been collected but not analyzed yet for any of the effects of concern here.

Purpose of the experiment, major hypotheses and expectations

This experiment is part of a multimethod study that also involves EEG and fMRI measurements in the same paradigm. In the current experiment, we explore the neural basis of quick, feedforward response activation by color stimuli. For this we employ a

response priming paradigm (Vorberg et al., 2003) where primes and targets consist of red and green color stimuli (Schmidt, 2000, 2002; Schmidt, Niehaus, & Nagel, 2006; Schmidt & Seydell, 2008). In this variant of the task, each trial consisted of a fixation period (duration: 767 ms), a flanker prime (two same-colored circles located left and right from the center, either both red or green; duration 50 ms), followed by a variable SOA (33, 83, 117, or 150 ms) during which a blank screen was presented, and, finally, the target stimulus (a single centrally located circle, either red or green; duration: 1017 ms), whose presentation duration also served as the response window. Participants were instructed to indicate the color or the target stimulus (2-interval yes-no task). A variable intertrial interval separated trials (duration jittered using optseq (<https://surfer.nmr.mgh.harvard.edu/optseq/>; Dale, 1999); $M = 5,025$ ms, $SD = 1,567$ ms, range: 2,000 to 8,000 ms). Participants completed 400 trials (50 trials per condition congruency [congruent, incongruent] x SOA [33, 83, 117, 150 ms]), split into 4 blocks à 100 trials. Assignment of keys to response options ("left" = "red" and "right" = "green", or vice versa) was counterbalanced across participants.

The behavioral properties of response priming by color are by now well understood and can be predicted quite exactly. Therefore the behavioral analysis in this experiment is not exploratory but mainly serves to ascertain that we are dealing with response priming proper.

In response priming experiments, both response times and error rates are of interest. Extensive previous research with keypress responses, pointing trajectories, force profiles, and lateralized readiness potentials has indicated that the motor response is first controlled exclusively by the prime and is taken over later by the actual target. The *Rapid Chase Theory of Response Priming* (Schmidt, Niehaus, & Nagel, 2006) explains this phenomenon by sequential waves of feedforward information coming first from the prime and then from the target, at a delay depending on the SOA. This model makes several hard predictions:

- the response priming effect increases with SOA (for SOAs up to about 100 ms),
- errors occur mainly in incongruent trials and there increase with SOA,
- errors are as fast as the fastest correct responses;
- the earliest responses are time-locked to the prime,
- the earliest responses go in the direction of the prime and are invariant with respect to all features of the target (including its identity and onset time).

To evaluate these predictions, we measure full *priming functions* where response times and error rates are plotted as a function of prime-target congruency (incongruent vs. congruent conditions) and prime-target SOA (varied parametrically in several steps).

Design, independent variables, dependent variables; variables that are not part of the analysis plan

We apply a completely crossed two-factorial repeated-measures design with factors of SOA (varied in four steps), and prime-target congruency (congruent, incongruent). Our intention was to realize SOAs of 33, 83, 117, 150 ms, but we have already noticed that not all SOAs were realized as intended in all branches of our multi-method study. Discrepancies will be made transparent in an eventual publication. Each participant participates in every condition over a course of four blocks of 100 trials (one experimental session). All behavioral analyses follow this same factorial structure.

Dependent variables are mean response times and error rates. Apart from the mean error rates, we apply hazard analysis and conditional accuracy functions where physical time is subdivided into time bins and the hazard rate of responding as well as accuracy of responses are plotted as a function of time (see our tutorial paper by Panis, F. Schmidt, Wolkersdorfer, & Schmidt, 2020). There are no further dependent variables.

Apart from the major independent variables, there are additional variables that are needed for counterbalancing purposes and the avoidance of experimental artifacts. Those are target identity (red or green) and keyboard mapping (which is counterbalanced between participants). Those balancing variables are not part of the analysis plan and are averaged across. The same holds for all participant variables, like gender, age, handedness, or other characteristics.

Criteria for data trimming, discarding of data or participants, or selective analyses

We rarely have to exclude participants from analysis after data are collected. We only do so if a participant clearly does not follow instructions. Indicators of that are very high error rates (close to chance level) on the target identification task or monotonic use of the same response key. Apart from that, sometimes participants' data cannot be used because of equipment malfunction, mistaken instructions, or other unforeseen events. In such cases, we try to recover as much of the valid data as we can. However, when a participant decides to abort an experiment prematurely we discard all data from that person. Finally, we exclude trials with problems in experimental timing, such as skipped monitor frames as measured by the timing feedback from the Psychophysics Toolbox. In experiments involving color discrimination, we screen participants for color deficiencies by using Ishihara plates.

Planned analyses, variable transformations

The major analysis strictly follows the two-factorial structure of the independent variables. We will apply two-factorial repeated-measures analysis of variances (ANOVA; factors Congruency and SOA) on mean response times as well as mean error rates. In the analyses of response times, only correct responses will be analyzed. Responses faster than 100 or slower than 999 ms are discarded as outliers, which should yield only a small percentage of outliers. Practice blocks are discarded. Error rates p are transformed into logits according to the formula $\text{logit} = \log [p/(1-p)]$, after replacing perfect error rates of 0 and 1 with values of $1/2r$ and $1 - 1/2r$, where r is the number of stimulus repetitions per participant. In other words, half of a response is added to or subtracted from any perfect score to prevent division by zero.

In fully crossed repeated-measures designs, we adjust standard error bars for intersubject variability (Loftus & Masson, 1994). Because the statistical models for repeated measures only use the interaction between the participant factor and the effect of interest as an error term, the main effect of the participant factor does not enter the error variance and can be discarded. Error bars should reflect the resulting increase in power to aid the graphical interpretation of the data. We use a very simple adjustment method (Bakeman & McArthur, 1996) where each participant's data pattern is vertically shifted by an additive constant until all individual means are equal to the grand mean (*ipsative data*). This way, the intersubject variance is zero while all interactions remain intact. Then standard errors are calculated across the adjusted participants as usual.

Statistical decision criteria and multiple tests

We generally report statistical tests as conventionally significant at a false-positive risk of $\alpha = .05$ because many readers use that criterion. However, internally we are more conservative and regard p -values between .01 and .05 as only mild evidence against the null hypothesis and would not base strong conclusions on such results. Greenhouse-Geisser correction is used for all tests irrespective of the outcome of a formal sphericity test.

Corrections for type-I error accumulation are handled in the following way. We follow the custom of not correcting the set of F tests within a single ANOVA model for multiple tests (two main effects and one interaction). We also follow the custom of not correcting F tests across the ANOVAS of different dependent variables. However, when we conduct k multiple tests *within* the frame of an analysis (e.g., analyzing priming effects separately for each SOA), we use a Bonferroni correction of $\alpha' = 1 - (1 - \alpha)^k$.

Foreseeable follow-up analyses

In many experiments, discoveries in the data lead to follow-up analyses. Furthermore, reviewers often request additional analyses. Examples would be learning effects (time-courses of effects across blocks or sessions), sequential effects (e.g., response times following error trials), or delta plots. We always clearly specify which analyses are planned (follow from the design) and which ones are post-hoc (based on discoveries).

Not every aspect of data analysis can be preplanned. For instance, it is always an executive decision to choose a good bin size for a histogram, a color code for a heat-map, or the minimum number of trials that allow for plotting a data point in a conditional-accuracy or hazard diagram. Unexpected problems may lead to unbalanced designs or unusual distributions of data, forcing analyzers to adjust statistical methods. Advances in methodological knowledge and creative development of methods may even lead to the replacement of one technique by a superior one. We believe that this is generally a sign of scientific progress, not of unwarranted researcher degrees of freedom. We are transparent about such issues and developments in our own analysis strategies and clearly identify them in our publications.

Sample size determination

In multi-factor repeated-measures designs, statistical power can be calculated if all effect sizes can be predicted along with their respective error variances. In practice, however, too many terms are unknown for a meaningful power analysis. Because the number of trials per participant and condition is about as important for power as the number of participants (Arend & Schäfer, 2019; Baker et al., 2020; Smith & Little, 2018), we control *measurement precision* at the level of individual participants in single tasks and stimulus conditions (Biafora & Schmidt, 2019; Lakens, 2024). For each task, we calculate precision as s/\sqrt{r} (Eisenhart, 1962), where s is a single participant's standard deviation in a given cell of the basic design (e.g., Consistency \times SOA) and r is the number of repeated measures in each cell and subject. We assume standard deviations of $SD = 60$ ms for response times (based on our own benchmark data) and the maximal possible standard deviation of .5 for error and accuracy rates. For instance, when $r = 100$, we can expect a precision of $60/\sqrt{100} = 6$ ms in individual response times and $0.5/\sqrt{100} = 0.05$ (five percentage points) in error/accuracy rates. This means that an uncorrected 95% confidence interval calculated within a single observer would be able to resolve mean differences of two precision units, $\approx 2s/\sqrt{r}$.

In the present experiments, $r = 50$, and we assume $SD(RT) = 60$ ms, $\max. SD(Error) = 0.5$. Therefore we expect a precision of 8.5 ms in response times and 7.1 percentage points in accuracy scores of each individual observer and condition. Precision thus approaches our previous recommendations for response priming studies ($r = 60$, F. Schmidt, Haberkamp, & Schmidt, 2011). We measure 34 observers in all experimental conditions.

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